

1 **Long-term high temperatures affect seed maturation and seed coat integrity in *Brassica***
2 ***napus***

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41

42 **SUMMARY**

- 43 • Temperatures above the optimum growth temperature affect seed development,
44 producing seeds with ruptured seed coats. This phenotype is associated with accelerated
45 embryo development. However, the molecular mechanism underlying this effect remains
46 unclear.
- 47 • To investigate the occurrence of temperature-induced seed coat rupture, we combined
48 detailed phenotyping approaches of oilseed rape seeds with transcriptomics, histology,
49 immunolabelling, hormone and cell wall profiling.
- 50 • Our data suggest that high temperatures accelerate embryo growth, resulting in the
51 formation of larger embryos but not larger seeds. The formation of large embryos
52 increased the mechanical pressure exerted by the embryo on the seed coat cells, reducing
53 their thickness. The seed coat began to mature prematurely with the accumulation of
54 demethylesterified pectin, possibly making the cell wall stiffer. Application of abscisic acid,
55 a hormone involved in seed dormancy, did not rescue the seed coat rupture phenotype.
56 Hormonal and transcriptional profiling indicated that the embryo did not enter dormancy.
- 57 • Prolonged high temperatures during seed development accelerated embryo growth by
58 stimulating cell division, while the seed coat, which depends on cell elongation, could not
59 withstand the tension exerted by the embryo, started seed maturation and eventually
60 ruptured.

61

62 **KEYWORDS**

63 *Brassica napus*, cell wall, long-term high temperature, pectin, seed coat rupture, seed
64 development

65

66 INTRODUCTION

67 The adverse impacts of global warming on agricultural production pose a major challenge to
68 global food security in the 21st century. Extreme weather events, such as heat stress, drought
69 and floods, have been observed to reduce crop yields and shorten growing seasons,
70 particularly in warm tropical regions. This has the potential to affect the production of staple
71 crops, such as rice, wheat, maize, and soybean (Zhao *et al.*, 2017; Agnolucci & De Lipsis, 2020;
72 Jägermeyr *et al.*, 2021; Heino *et al.*, 2023). The mean global temperature increase in 2023 was
73 1.36°C above preindustrial levels (National Aeronautics and Space Administration, 2024),
74 highlighting the need to adapt agricultural practices to higher temperatures.

75 *Brassica napus* (canola or oilseed rape), an allotetraploid species in the Brassicaceae family,
76 is the second most widely cultivated oilseed crop, used for the production of vegetable oil,
77 biofuel, and protein in animal feed. Cultivation of oilseed rape at temperatures above the
78 optimum growth temperature of 21°C for prolonged periods, especially during the flowering
79 stage, resulted in several adverse effects, including rapid vegetative growth, reduced viability
80 of female gametophytes, increased seed abortion rate, accelerated embryo development,
81 and a reduction in seed oil composition (Young *et al.*, 2004; Mácová *et al.*, 2022; Secchi *et al.*,
82 2023). One of the distinctive phenotypes observed during seed development of certain canola
83 cultivars subjected to prolonged heat stress that affects seed yield is the occurrence of the
84 preharvest sprouting phenotype (PHS) (Mácová *et al.*, 2022). Misregulation of seed dormancy
85 by abscisic acid and dormancy-related genes is considered to be the main cause of PHS in
86 many cereal crops (Benech-Arnold & Rodríguez, 2018; Tai *et al.*, 2021). This phenotype is
87 associated with seed coat rupture (SCR), which is observed in seeds during the early stages of
88 maturation. The exact molecular mechanism by which this phenotype is produced at elevated
89 temperatures remains unclear.

90 In Brassicaceae, seed size is regulated by the interaction between maternal and zygotic signals
91 that coordinate the proper development of the seed coat, endosperm, and embryo (Li *et al.*,
92 2019). During the maturation of *Arabidopsis* seeds, the pressure generated by the interaction
93 between the developing embryo and the endosperm within the seed, driven by embryo
94 growth, exerts tension on the developing integuments (Creff *et al.*, 2015, 2023). The tension

95 generated by zygotic tissues is sensed by a specific layer of the seed coat's outer integument,
96 the adaxial epidermis (oi1). This mechanical stimulus triggers a transcriptional response
97 marked by the activation of the mechanosensitive gene *EUI-like P450A1 (ELA1)*, which is
98 believed to promote cell wall stiffening through demethylesterified pectin accumulation
99 regulating seed size (Creff *et al.*, 2023). The dry mass of the primary plant cell wall is composed
100 of cellulose, hemicellulose, and pectin (Cosgrove, 2024). Pectin forms a hydrated gel-like
101 matrix in which cellulose and hemicellulose cross-link to form the cell wall. It is abundant in
102 the middle lamella, an adhesive layer between adjacent cells. The most abundant pectin,
103 homogalacturonan (HG), is produced in a methylesterified state, which can be
104 demethylesterified by the activity of pectin methylesterase (PME) (Turbant *et al.*, 2016; Wu
105 *et al.*, 2018). Blockwise removal of methyl groups can lead to the formation of Ca²⁺ cross-links,
106 which increase the wall stiffness and inhibit growth. Alternatively, random removal can lead
107 to pectin degradation, affecting wall rheology (Wu *et al.*, 2018).

108 Seed size correlates with endosperm proliferation and development. The two processes are
109 linked by a brassinosteroid-induced cell expansion and increased levels of methylesterified
110 pectin in the seed coat, which helps to regulate seed size (Lima *et al.*, 2024). Mechanical
111 constriction of seed size, which restricts embryo growth, triggers the maturation programme
112 by increasing lipid and protein storage and inhibiting embryonic cell divisions (Rolletschek *et*
113 *al.*, 2021, 2024). In this study, we used a multi-method approach to investigate the occurrence
114 of the temperature-induced SCR phenotype. The results show that SCR occurs in seeds around
115 20 days after pollination (20 DAP) when plants are cultivated at elevated temperatures for a
116 prolonged period. The pressure induced by unrestricted embryo growth led to increased
117 tension in the seed coat, characterised by reduced thickness of the seed coat layers, and
118 resulted in early changes in cell wall composition. Accumulation of demethylesterified pectin
119 may stiffen the cell wall of the seed coat, which may break despite being stiffened or may
120 promote pectin degradation making the seed coat more breakable. The precise mechanism
121 by which accelerated embryo development influences heat stress-mediated seed
122 development in oilseed rape plants remains to be elucidated. A deeper understanding of the
123 effects of prolonged elevated temperatures on seed development could prove invaluable in
124 the generation of thermotolerant varieties of canola varieties, which would help to improve
125 crop yields in the context of global warming in the 21st century.

126

127 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

128 **Plant materials and growth conditions**

129 Two *Brassica napus* spring cultivars, Topas DH4079 and Westar, were used for this study.
130 Seeds were sterilised, germinated, and grown initially in the phytotron (21°C, 16/8 h long day
131 period, 150 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$) until the emergence of the first flowering buds, as previously
132 mentioned (Máková *et al.*, 2022). Plants are then transferred to greenhouse chambers with
133 control temperature treatment (CT) and heat treatment (HT) conditions maintained under a
134 long-day regime (16 h light/8 h dark), LED lights with a light intensity of 150 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 35%–
135 45% humidity, 18°C during the night and 21°C (CT) and 32°C (HT) during the day. Seeds used
136 for the experiments are obtained from hand-pollinated flowers. The age of the seeds is
137 counted from the day after pollination (DAP).

138

139 **Seed phenotyping**

140 Ten hand-pollinated and dried siliques from eight plants in three biological replicates from CT
141 and HT conditions were screened for the total, viable, dead seeds and seeds undergoing SCR
142 (seed coat rupture with radicle or cotyledon protrusion). Fresh seeds from 14 DAP to 20 DAP
143 were collected from Topas and Westar growing at CT and HT for embryo staging. The whole
144 seed and its isolated embryo were imaged using a Levenhuk M500 base digital camera
145 attached to a Zeiss stemi 305 stereomicroscope. Images were used to measure the seed and
146 embryo areas using ImageJ from 14, 18, and 20 DAP from both conditions. The ratio of the
147 embryo-to-seed area was calculated to get information on the space occupied by the embryo
148 within the seed at each stage of development. Statistical significance was accounted for by a
149 two-way ANOVA test with Sidak's multiple comparisons (* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.005$, *** $p <$
150 0.0005 , and **** $p < 0.00005$).

151

152 **Hormonal measurements**

153 Two experiments were performed. First, the hormone profiling was done on 14, 20, 26, and
154 36 DAP whole seeds collected from CT or HT in five replicates, each pooled from three plants.
155 The 20, 26, and 36 DAP seeds collected from HT showing an SCR phenotype were separately
156 collected and analysed. A second experiment was carried out on isolated embryos and seed
157 coats of 14 and 18 DAP seeds collected from CT or HT in four replicates, each pooled from
158 three plants. Abscisates, auxins (except indole-3-pyruvic acid; IPyA), and gibberellins were

159 determined using ultra-high-performance liquid chromatograph I-Class (Waters, Milford, CT,
160 USA) coupled with tandem mass spectrometer Xevo TQ-XS (Waters, Manchester, UK)
161 according to the "hormonomics" methodology (Šimura *et al.*, 2018). Approximately 10 mg of
162 fresh weight of each sample was aliquoted into microtubes. One ml of 60% aqueous
163 acetonitrile (v/v), a mixture of stabile isotopic labelled internal standards, and four ceramic
164 extraction beads were added into the tube. The samples were shaken in a Retsch MM400
165 oscillation mill (Haan, Germany) at 27 Hz for 5 min, sonicated for 3 min, and incubated for 30
166 min in a refrigerator. Allegra 64R benchtop centrifuge (Beckman Coulter, USA) at 20,000 rpm
167 for 15 minutes was used to separate the pellet from the supernatant. The supernatant was
168 loaded onto Oasis® HLB 30 mg/1 cc extraction cartridge (Waters, Milford, CT, USA) previously
169 activated with 1 ml methanol, water, and 60% aqueous acetonitrile (v/v). The cartridge was
170 finally washed with 60% aqueous acetonitrile (v/v). The flow-through and wash fractions were
171 collected into borosilicate glass tubes (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The samples were
172 evaporated in a SpeedVac concentrator (RC1010 Centrivap Jouan, ThermoFisher, USA) and
173 reconstructed in 40 µl of 25% aqueous acetonitrile (v/v). Five µl were injected onto Acquity
174 UPLC® CSHTM 1.7 µm, 2.1x150 mm chromatographic column and eluted using a gradient
175 elution of acidified water and acetonitrile. Data were acquired in a multiple reaction
176 monitoring mode. The detailed chromatographic and mass spectrometry conditions are
177 provided by Šimura *et al.* (2018). Data were processed with MassLynx V4.2 software (Waters,
178 Manchester, UK), and the concentrations of determined plant hormones were calculated
179 using the isotope dilution method. Endogenous IPyA was determined following the protocol
180 described by Pěnčík *et al.* (2018). Approximately 10 mg (fresh weight) samples were extracted
181 in 1 ml of cold 50 mmol/l phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) containing 0.1% sodium
182 diethyldithiocarbamate and isotope-labelled internal standard of IPyA. A 200 µl aliquot was
183 derivatised with cysteamine, acidified to pH 2.7 with HCl, and purified using in-tip µSPE. Eluted
184 samples were evaporated under reduced pressure, reconstituted in 10% aqueous methanol,
185 and analysed using an HPLC system 1260 Infinity II (Agilent Technologies, USA) equipped with
186 a Kinetex C18 column (50 mmx2.1 mm, 1.7 µm; Phenomenex) and coupled to 6495 Triple
187 Quad detector (Agilent Technologies, USA).

188

189 **ABA treatment**

190 ABA treatment was performed by culturing 15 siliques of 14 DAP and 18 DAP from HT and CT
191 conditions, respectively, collected from three plants in three biological replicates. The siliques
192 were cut at the pedicel region, collected, surface-sterilised with 70% ethanol, air dried, and
193 cultured in 50 ml tubes with 20 ml of ½ MS with 0.8% plant agar, 0.05% plant preservative for
194 tissue culture media (Plant Tissue Culture Technologies) and supplemented with 10 µM ABA
195 (Duchefa Biochemie) or the same volume of DMSO as negative control. A representative
196 picture of the cultured siliques is shown in Fig. S1. The silique culture was incubated in the
197 greenhouse with the other plants to simulate the same temperature conditions. The total,
198 viable, dead and SCR seed numbers were manually estimated on dried siliques under a Zeiss
199 stemi 305 stereomicroscope.

200

201 **RNA extraction and sequencing**

202 RNA was extracted from 50 mg of ground tissue of 14 DAP, 18 DAP, 20 DAP normal, and 20
203 DAP SCR seeds from CT and HT, collected from three plants in four biological replicates using
204 a NucleoSpin RNA Plant and Fungi kit (Macherey-Nagel) following the manufacturer's
205 protocol. The samples were treated with RNase-free rDNase (Macherey-Nagel) and repurified
206 using the RNeasy MinElute Cleanup Kit (Qiagen). The samples were sequenced by Novogene
207 Genomic Sequencing Labs. After sample quality control and library preparation, paired-end
208 short-read RNA sequencing was performed on poly-A RNA using an Illumina Novaseq
209 Sequencing platform. Quality check of raw paired-end fastq reads was carried out by FastQC
210 (Andrews, 2010), and their origin was categorised using BioBloomTools v2.3.4 (Chu *et al.*,
211 2014). The Illumina adapters and quality trimming of raw fastq reads were performed using
212 Trimmomatic v0.39 (Bolger *et al.*, 2014) with settings CROP:250 LEADING:3 TRAILING:3
213 SLIDINGWINDOW:4:5 MINLEN:35. Trimmed RNA-Seq reads were mapped to the *Brassica*
214 *napus* genome (genome build: Bra_napus_v2.0) with gene annotation (NCBI *Brassica napus*
215 Annotation Release 101) using STAR v2.7.3a (Dobin *et al.*, 2013) as splice-aware short read
216 aligner and default parameters except outFilterMismatchNoverLmax 0.1 and twopassMode
217 Basic. Quality control after alignment concerning the number and percentage of uniquely-
218 and multi-mapped reads, rRNA contamination, mapped regions, read coverage distribution,
219 strand specificity, gene biotypes, and PCR duplication was performed using RSeQC v4.0.0
220 (Wang *et al.*, 2012), Picard toolkit v2.25.6 (Picard toolkit, 2018), Qualimap v.2.2.2
221 (Okonechnikov *et al.*, 2016). All compatible results and statistics were processed by MultiQC

222 v1.10.1 (Ewels *et al.*, 2016). The sequence data have been deposited in the NCBI under the
223 Bio-Project PRJNA1188476 (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA1188476>).

224 The differential gene expression analysis was calculated based on the gene counts produced
225 using featureCounts from Subread package v2.0 (Liao *et al.*, 2014) and further analysed by
226 Bioconductor package DESeq2 v1.34.0 (Love *et al.*, 2014). Because of its conservative features
227 and to prevent false positive results, data produced by DESeq2 with independent filtering
228 were chosen for the differential gene expression analysis. Genes were considered to be
229 differentially expressed based on a cut-off for adjusted p-value ≤ 0.05 and $\log_2FC \geq 1$ or ≤ -1 .
230 Clustered heatmaps were generated from selected top differentially regulated genes using R
231 package pheatmap v1.0.12 (Kolde, 2015), volcano plots were produced using ggplot2 v3.3.5
232 package (Wickham, 2011), and MA plots were generated using ggpubr v0.4.0 package
233 (Kassambara, 2018). GO enrichment is done taking all the Entrez gene IDs and cross-mapping
234 them against UniProt IDs, then taking all the transcript sequences and mapping them (using
235 BLAST) against the NCBI Nucleotide database subset for all species under taxons 3701
236 (*Arabidopsis* genus) and 981071 (*Brassicaceae* tribe) obtaining RefSeq gene IDs which were
237 cross-mapped against UniProt IDs and then used in GO enrichment. The co-expression cluster
238 analysis is described in Method S1.

239

240 **Seed embedding and sectioning**

241 Seeds were fixed in FAA (45% ethanol, 5% acetic acid and 1.85% formaldehyde) for 24 h under
242 vacuum, followed by another incubation at 4°C for 24 h in fresh FAA. The seeds were washed
243 once with water. Tissue softening was done with Franklin Maceration solution (1:1 v/v of 30%
244 H₂O₂ and glacial acetic acid) for 4 h at 60°C. Dehydration was done using 10, 20, 30, 40, 50,
245 60% ethanol series in 10% glycerine for 1 h at 30°C, followed by 4 days in 70% ethanol at 4°C
246 and dehydration with 80, 90 and 95% ethanol for 1 h at room temperature. Infiltration and
247 embedding with Technovit 7100 (Kulzer Technik GmbH) were performed according to the
248 manufacturer's protocol with the following modifications. The initial infiltration was
249 performed in a 50% infiltration solution in ethanol overnight at room temperature, followed
250 by incubation for one week at 4°C in 100% infiltration solution with 1% w/v Technovit 7100
251 Hardener I. Embedding was performed with 6.6% w/v Technovit 7100 Hardener II in
252 infiltration solution and incubated for 8 days at -18°C to delay initial polymerisation. The
253 samples were then incubated at room temperature to complete the polymerisation process.

254 The 3- μ m sections were prepared with a Leica RM2235 microtome using an attached
255 stainless-steel knife.

256

257 **Toluidine blue staining**

258 The sections were stained with 0.05% Toluidine blue (Acros Organics) for 1 minute, followed
259 by four washes of 3 minutes each. Mounting was done on dried slides with Entellan (Sigma-
260 Aldrich). Imaging of the sections was performed using a Zeiss AxioImager microscope. The
261 thickness of the seed coat layers was measured in twenty regions per section, for three
262 sections per seed and ten seeds per sample, using Image J. Graphs were plotted with
263 significance calculated using a two-way ANOVA test with Tukey multiple comparisons.

264

265 **Staining of lignin and pectin**

266 Seven seeds at 14 and 18 DAP from CT and HT and 22 DAP from CT were used. Pectin was
267 detected using a 0.05% w/v Ruthenium Red stain (Sigma-Aldrich) in an aqueous solution.
268 Sections were rehydrated before staining for 7 minutes, followed by two wash steps with
269 water, and mounted in Entellan (Sigma-Aldrich). Lignin was detected with 0.5% Safranin-O
270 (Acros organics) in an aqueous solution followed by three washes in water. Slides were
271 mounted in Entellan (Sigma-Aldrich). Imaging was done using a Zeiss AxioImager microscope.

272

273 **Immunolabelling**

274 Seeds at 10, 14, and 18 DAP from CT and HT, in two biological replicates, were fixed in 4% w/v
275 paraformaldehyde in ice-cold PEM buffer (50 mM PIPES, 5 mM EGTA, and 5 mM MgSO₄, pH
276 6.9). Samples were incubated on ice under vacuum for twice 1 h with fresh fixative solution,
277 followed by overnight incubation at 4°C. The samples were washed twice with ice-cold PEM
278 buffer, dehydrated through an ethanol series (50%, 70%, 80%, 90% and 100% three times)
279 under vacuum and infiltrated with increasing concentrations (30%, 50% and 100%) of LR white
280 resin (Agar Scientific) in absolute ethanol over 8 days before being polymerised at 60°C for 24
281 h. Six seeds by timepoint per growth condition per biological replicate were sectioned (1 μ m
282 thickness) using a glass knife mounted on a Leica RM2265 or EM UC7 microtome.
283 Immunolocalizations were performed with JIM5, LM19, LM20, and LM25 antibodies
284 (Agrisera). For immunolocalisation with LM25, an incubation with 0.1% pectolyase in 1X PBS
285 was done for 25 min at room temperature and washed once in 1X PBS before the blocking

286 step. For immunolocalisation with JIM5, LM19, and LM25, the sections were blocked with 3%
287 w/v BSA in 1X PBS and incubated for 1 h at room temperature. For the immunolocalisation
288 with LM20, an incubation in CAPS buffer (50 mM CAPS and 2 mM CaCl₂) for 1 h followed by
289 three washes with 1x PBS was performed before blocking with 3% skimmed milk in 1X PBS.
290 Sections were incubated with 1:10 v/v dilution of antibody prepared with 1% BSA in 1X PBS
291 for JIM5, LM19 and LM25 and 1% skimmed milk in 1X PBS for LM20 overnight at 4°C in a
292 humid chamber. The sections were brought to room temperature for 1 h, washed three times
293 with the above-mentioned buffers and incubated for 1 h in a humid chamber in the dark with
294 the secondary antibodies. A dilution of 1:100 v/v of secondary antibodies [anti-rat IgG Alexa
295 488 (Thermo Fisher) or anti-rat IgG Dylight 488 (Agrisera) for JIM5 and anti-rat IgM Dylight
296 488 (Thermo Fisher) for LM19, LM20 and LM25] in 1% BSA or 1% skimmed milk in 1X PBS was
297 used. Sections were washed in the respective buffers and 1X PBS, counterstained with 0.025
298 mg/ml Calcofluor white (Sigma-Aldrich), and mounted with VECTASHIELD antifade mounting
299 medium (Eurobio). The images were obtained with the ZEISS Axioimager 2 with a 40X dry
300 objective.

301 The intensity of the immunofluorescence in the cell walls of the epidermal and palisade layers
302 of the seed coat was quantified using ImageJ software. Images were adjusted using min/max
303 settings for optimal representation of fluorescent signals. For the three epidermal layers, a
304 segmented line with a width of 25 points was used to manually mark the cell walls of adjacent
305 cells of the same layer. The sum of fluorescence intensity in the three epidermal layers was
306 represented as one measurement. A region of interest was marked using the polygon
307 selection tool for the palisade layer. The mean fluorescence value obtained over the marked
308 regions for the different layers was subtracted from the background signal over the same area
309 to obtain the final fluorescence intensity.

310

311 **Cell wall profiling from the seed coat**

312 The enzymatic fingerprinting of the cell wall of seed coat from 10, 14 and 18 DAP seeds grown
313 under CT and HT conditions was performed in three biological replicates. The seed coats were
314 dissected from the seeds and were submerged in 96% (v/v) ethanol. The ethanol fraction was
315 discarded, and the seed coats were dried in a speed vacuum concentrator at 30°C overnight.
316 Dried seed coats were digested with 5 U/mg DW sample of *Pectobacterium carotovorum*
317 endo-polygalacturonase or *Paenibacillus* sp. xyloglucanase (Megazyme, Bray, Ireland) in 50

318 mM ammonium acetate buffer (pH 5) at 37°C for 18 h. Samples were centrifuged at 13,000
319 rpm for 10 min, and 100 µl of the supernatants were transferred into vials. For MS analysis,
320 10 µl of each fraction was injected. The oligosaccharides released from digestion were
321 separated according to Voxeur et al. (2019). Xyloglucan and pectin fragments were analysed
322 using an HPLC system (UltiMate 3000 RS HPLC system, Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA)
323 coupled to an Impact II Ultra-High Resolution Qq-Time-Of-Flight (UHR-QqTOF) spectrometer
324 (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany) equipped with an electrospray ionisation (ESI) source
325 in negative mode with the end plate offset set voltage to 500 V, capillary voltage to 4000 V,
326 nebuliser to 40 psi, dry gas to 8 l/min and dry temperature of 180°C. The Compass 1.8
327 software (Bruker Daltonics) was used to acquire the data. Chromatographic separation was
328 performed on an ACQUITY UPLC Protein BEH SEC Column (125A, 1.7 µm, 4.6 mm X 300 mm,
329 Waters Corporation, Milford, MA, USA) coupled with guard Column BEH SEC Column (125A,
330 1.7 µm, 4.6 mm X 30 mm). Elution was performed in 50 mM ammonium formate and 0.1%
331 formic acid at a flow rate of 0.4 ml/min and with a column oven temperature of 40°C.

332

333 **Space-restricted growth of siliques**

334 A 3-mm cross-section silicone tube was inserted over 10 DAP and 12 DAP siliques growing on
335 plants under HT and CT conditions, respectively, in three biological replicates with 20 siliques
336 per replicate. A 10 DAP silique at HT has a similar silique thickness to a 12 DAP silique at CT.
337 Siliques from the age and growth conditions without a silicone tube were used as a negative
338 control. The number of total, viable, dead and SCR seeds per dried silique were counted.

339

340 **Statistical analysis**

341 GraphPad Prism v.8.4.3 was used to plot the graphs and calculate the statistical significance
342 using either ANOVA or multiple comparison tests. R programming was used to analyse the
343 data and obtain the statistical significance for the RNA sequencing experiment.

344

345 **RESULTS**

346 ***Brassica napus* seed coat integrity is affected by long-term heat stress**

347 We have previously reported that in *Brassica napus* cv. Topas the early seed development is
348 affected under long-term heat treatment (HT) (Máková *et al.*, 2022). This study focuses on
349 the seed coat rupture (SCR) observed in seeds of Topas developed under HT, starting at 20

350 DAP, while this phenomenon has never been observed in seeds grown under control
351 treatment (CT) (Fig. 1a-e). The SCR phenotype occurred with variable outcomes, from a minor
352 seed coat break with the embryo remaining intact within the seed to a complete testa rupture
353 resulting in the embryo root or shoot protruding through the break site. Such embryos often
354 had distinguishable phenotypes (Fig. 1c,d). The quantification of the phenotypes on dry seeds
355 revealed a significantly reduced number of total viable seeds produced per silique,
356 accompanied by a significant increase in the proportion of dead seeds and seeds with an SCR
357 phenotype per silique in HT-grown siliques. At HT, approximately 50% of the seeds in a silique
358 underwent SCR (Fig. 1e). Embryo staging of the seeds from 14 to 20 DAP indicated that
359 embryo development is accelerated in seeds developed under HT compared to seeds grown
360 under CT (Fig. 1f), which is consistent with our previous observations in seeds at early
361 developmental stages (Máková *et al.*, 2022). We estimated that the embryos in the seeds at
362 HT were four days ahead of the embryos in seeds at CT in their developmental stage, e.g., a
363 14 DAP embryo at HT would be developmentally similar to an 18 DAP embryo at CT (Fig. 1f).
364 Based on these observations, we designated 14 and 18 DAP HT seeds as early maturing seeds
365 and HT seeds after 20 DAP as late maturing seeds.

366

367

368 **Fig. 1.** SCR phenotype observed in Topas seeds developed under HT. (a, b) 26 DAP seeds (a)
369 and their isolated embryos (b) grown under CT. (c, d) 26 DAP seeds (c) and their isolated
370 embryos (d) grown under HT. SCR was observed (*, Δ , +, \bullet). * Indicates seeds with testa
371 rupture with intact embryo, Δ indicates testa rupture with radicle protrusion, + indicates testa

372 rupture with cotyledon protrusion, and ● indicates embryos with abnormal development. (e)
373 Quantification of the number of dry seeds per silique from CT (blue) and HT (red) showing the
374 number of total, viable, SCR and dead seeds. Asterisks indicate statistically significant
375 differences in HT in a multiple t-test using the Holm-Sidak method (**** corresponds to p -
376 values of $p < 0.0001$. (f) Embryo stage of seeds developed on CT (top) and HT (bottom) from
377 14 to 20 DAP. The isolated embryo shown on the right is from the seed on the left. Scale bars:
378 2 mm (a-d) and 3mm (f).

379

380 **Unbalanced hormonal profiles of the seeds at HT may affect seed maturation**

381 The observed SCR phenotype led us to hypothesise that HT may deregulate seed dormancy
382 and maturation programs by affecting the homeostasis of the plant hormones abscisic acid,
383 gibberellins, and auxin. GA and its metabolites were below the detection limit, preventing any
384 conclusions about the influence of HT on their levels. In the seeds at 20, 26, and 36 DAP
385 developed under HT, ABA and IAA levels are significantly and age-dependently reduced (Fig.
386 2a; Fig. S2). The levels of the auxin precursor anthranilate (ANT) were significantly lower in 14
387 DAP HT embryos. In contrast, the levels of tryptophan (TRP) and indole-pyruvic acid (IPyA) in
388 14 DAP HT embryos and indole-3-acetonitrile (IAN) in 18 DAP HT embryos were significantly
389 higher compared to CT (Fig. S2). However, the levels of IAA in the CT and HT embryos at 14 or
390 18 DAP were not significantly different because the degradation products such as 2-
391 oxoindole-3-acetic acid (oxIAA) and IAA-aspartate (IAA-Asp) were significantly higher in the
392 embryos developed under HT. The levels of auxin metabolites in the seed coat were similar
393 to those observed in the embryos, except for a significant increase in IAA levels at HT. The IAA
394 levels were significantly reduced in mature seeds (20, 26 and 36 DAP). However, IAA levels in
395 intact and SCR seeds were not different (Fig. S2).

396 A significant increase in the levels of active ABA and its catabolic products (7-hydroxy-ABA,
397 phaseic acid (PA) and dihydrophaseic acid (DPA)) was observed in the embryos of 14 and 18
398 DAP seeds, whereas no significant changes were identified in the isolated seed coat (Fig. 2b).
399 When embryo stage was taken into account and ABA levels in 14 DAP embryos from HT were
400 compared with those in 18 DAP embryos from CT, no significant differences were found. ABA
401 levels were significantly reduced in 26 and 36 DAP mature seeds developed under HT, with
402 no significant difference between intact and SCR seeds (Fig. 2a). These reduced ABA and IAA
403 levels in mature seeds led to the hypothesis of reduced seed dormancy in HT.

404
 405 **Fig. 2.** ABA levels and expression of genes involved in ABA metabolism in *Brassica napus* Topas
 406 seeds. (a) Seeds were from 14 DAP to 36 DAP of CT (blue) and HT (red, dark red). From 20
 407 DAP, HT seeds were separated into intact seeds (red) and SCR seeds (dark red). Quantification
 408 is presented as pmol per g fresh weight. (b) Measurements were performed for ABA, phaseic
 409 acid (PA), and dihydrophaseic acid (DPA) from embryos and seed coats from 14 DAP and 18
 410 DAP seeds grown in CT (blue) and HT (red). Asterisks indicate statistically significant
 411 differences in HT and between 14 DAP HT and 18 DAP CT in a multiple t-test using the Holm-
 412 Sidak method (*, **, *** and **** correspond to p -values of $0.05 > p > 0.01$, $0.01 > p > 0.001$,
 413 $0.001 > p > 0.0001$ and $p < 0.0001$, respectively); n.s., not significant. (c) 15 siliques of 14 DAP
 414 and 18 DAP from HT and CT, respectively, were cultured in the presence or absence of 10 μ M
 415 ABA (Fig. S1). Dry seeds were quantified for the number of total viable, SCR and dead seeds
 416 per silique. Samples with the same letter were not statistically significantly different. (d)
 417 Relative expression of selected genes representing DORMANCY ASSOCIATED gene 1 (DRM1)
 418 and FRUCTOSE 1,6-BIPHOSPHATE ALDOLASE 6 (FBA6) in 14 DAP (blue), 20 DAP intact (yellow)
 419 and 20 DAP SCR (grey) seeds. Data were extracted from the transcriptome dataset (Tables S1
 420 and S2). (e) Heatmap showing the differential expression of selected genes involved in ABA
 421 metabolism in 14 DAP, 20 DAP intact, and 20 DAP SCR seeds. The full dataset is provided in
 422 Tables S1 and S2.

423

424 **ABA treatment on the siliques did not restore the SCR phenotype**

425 To test whether the reduced ABA in the seeds was one of the causes of the SCR phenotype
426 and reduced seed dormancy at HT, we cultured the Topas siliques in the presence of 10 μ M
427 ABA in an *in vitro* silique culture experiment. The number of seeds undergoing SCR at HT in
428 the siliques cultured with ABA was not significantly different from that in untreated siliques
429 (Fig. 2c). Moreover, *in vitro* silique culture appeared to partially rescue SCR at HT compared
430 to seeds developed in siliques attached to the plants, most likely due to the increased
431 humidity of the culture setup (Fig. S1). Thus, the cultured siliques produced more viable seeds.
432 Comparable results were observed with different modes of exogenous application of ABA to
433 individual siliques and in an *in vitro* seed culture (data not shown).

434

435 **The embryo-to-seed size ratio is increased at HT**

436 We observed that seed development in Topas and Westar was accelerated under long-term
437 high-temperature growth, with embryos exhibiting a four-day advance in maturity under HT
438 compared to CT (Fig. 1, Fig. S3, Mácová et al., 2022). The SCR rate for Topas seeds was higher
439 than that for Westar seeds (Mácová et al., 2022). We hypothesised that this accelerated
440 embryo growth may interfere with seed development, thereby inducing the SCR phenotype.
441 We compared seed area and embryo area in seeds from 14 to 20 DAP at CT and HT in both
442 cultivars. The seed area increased from 14 to 20 DAP, and this increase was reduced from 20
443 DAP as the seeds entered the maturation phase (Fig. 3a, c). In Topas, the seed size at 18 DAP
444 was significantly larger under HT than under CT (Fig. 3a). In Westar, seeds were slightly larger
445 under HT at 14 DAP and smaller at 20 DAP (Fig. 3c). It should be noted that the seeds of the
446 Westar cultivar were larger on average than those of the Topas cultivar. Embryos at HT were
447 more than twice the size of those at the same DAP at CT for each DAP in both cultivars (Fig.
448 3b, d). These observations suggest that the seeds did not undergo a compensatory increase
449 in size to accommodate the HT-induced enlargement of the embryos. The embryo-to-seed
450 area ratio provides valuable insight into the space occupied by the embryo within the seed at
451 a given DAP under the two growth conditions (Fig. 3e). We observed that the embryos
452 developed under HT filled significantly more space in the seed than those grown under CT.
453 Furthermore, the embryo-to-seed area ratio in Topas was significantly higher than that in
454 Westar at 20 DAP. These observations suggest that the accelerated embryo growth in HT
455 resulted in the formation of larger embryos but not larger seeds.

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470 **The formation of larger embryos at HT impacts the thickness of the seed coat cells**

471 We wondered whether the presence of larger embryos in these seeds might affect the seed

472 coat cells, leading to SCR. The seed coat of *B. napus* is composed of three layers of cells (Fig.

473 4a): an outer epidermal layer of three cell files, a middle palisade layer made of a single layer
 474 of cells with substantial secondary cell walls, and an inner endothelial layer surrounding the
 475 endosperm (Jiang & Deyholos, 2010). The thickness of these three layers of the seed coat was
 476 measured in seeds of 10, 14, 18, 20, and 22 DAP developed under CT and HT (Fig. 4f-h). Seed
 477 coat thickness was not affected by HT in 10 DAP seeds (Fig. 4f-h). However, all three seed coat
 478 layers were significantly thinner in older seeds developed under HT (Fig. 4b-h). The palisade
 479 and the first endothelial layers were the most affected by this reduction, with a 46% reduction
 480 in endothelial cell layer thickness induced by HT as the seed aged from 14 DAP to 20 DAP,
 481 whereas the thickness reduction was only 12% at CT (Fig. 4i). These results indicate that the
 482 HT-induced embryo growth from 14 DAP increased tension on the cells of the developing seed
 483 coat, reducing its thickness due to cell stretching.

484
 485 **Fig. 4** The thickness of the seed coat cells is reduced in HT. (a-e) Histological sections of Topas
 486 seeds focused on the seed coat, stained with toluidine blue. (a) The seed coat is composed of
 487 an epidermal layer, a palisade layer and an endodermal layer. (b-e) Seed coat of 14 DAP seeds

488 from CT (b) and HT (d) and 18 DAP seeds from CT (c) and HT (e). Scale bars represent 200 μm .
489 (f-h) Box-whisker plots show the size mean, median, outliers, and SD in μm of the thickness
490 of the epidermal layer (f), palisade layer (g) and first endothelial cell layer (h) in 10, 14, 18,
491 and 20 DAP seeds from CT (blue) and HT (red). Samples with the same letter were not
492 statistically significantly different. (i) Percentage of reduction in thickness as the seed aged
493 from 14 to 20 DAP.

494

495 **Transcriptional regulation of the dormancy regulators provides a conflicting picture of the** 496 **HT effects on seed dormancy**

497 To gain an insight into the molecular mechanisms of SCR at HT in Topas, we performed
498 transcriptional profiling of seeds developed under HT and CT conditions at 14, 18 and 20 DAP,
499 including seeds without (20NSHT samples) and seeds with (20SHT samples) SCR phenotypes
500 at 20 DAP. Principal component analysis (PCA) using gene expression data from all the
501 samples was used to test for differences between samples and biological replicates. The PCA
502 revealed that the 14 DAP HT samples clustered with the 18 and 20 DAP CT samples,
503 correlating with the advanced embryo stage of the 14 DAP HT seeds (Fig. 5a). High-quality
504 clean reads were used for the differential expression gene (DEG) and gene ontology (GO)
505 enrichment analysis. Many misregulated (up- and down-regulated) DEGs, shown as Venn
506 diagrams (Fig. S4), were identified in our comparisons of samples from the same DAP: 14HT
507 vs. 14CT, 18HT vs. 18CT, and 20NSHT vs. 20SHT and 20CT, and of samples from the same
508 embryo stage (14HT vs. 18CT). The significant GO terms associated with the transcriptional
509 response of the seeds to HT conditions are related to cell cycle, development, hormonal
510 regulation, heat stress and changes in metabolic pathways (Fig. S5, Table S3).

511 To better understand the relationship between the HT-induced SCR phenotype, hormonal
512 deregulation, and seed dormancy, we first focused the analysis on the differential expression
513 of the dormancy gene markers DORMANCY ASSOCIATED gene 1 (DRM1) (Rae *et al.*, 2013) and
514 FRUCTOSE 1,6-BIPHOSPHATE ALDOLASE 6 (FBA6) (Lu *et al.*, 2012), genes involved in ABA
515 metabolism and signalling, and previously identified transcription factors involved in
516 dormancy regulation. We did not observe any significant difference between the 20SHT and
517 20NSHT (Fig. 2d,e; Fig. 5b; Table S2), possibly because the molecular information leading to
518 the SCR might already be encoded in younger seeds. The BnaDRM1 LOC106451187 and
519 LOC106437808 genes are highly expressed in dormant tissues (Rae *et al.*, 2013) and were

520 downregulated in 14HT and 20HT seeds (Fig. 2d). The BnaFBA6 LOC106391482 gene, which is
521 involved in the sugar metabolism pathway (Lu *et al.*, 2012), was upregulated in 14HT and
522 20HT seeds. The misregulation of these two dormancy markers indicates that seeds under HT
523 may have a reduced dormancy state. Expression of the following enzymes involved in ABA
524 biosynthesis (Wu *et al.*, 2023), zeaxanthin epoxidase BnaABA1 (LOC106390346), 9-cis-
525 epoxy-carotenoid dioxygenase BnaNCED9 (LOC106354700), dehydrogenase reductase
526 BnaABA2 (LOC106390565), and abscisic aldehyde oxidase BnaAAO3 (LOC106446766), was
527 significantly lower at 14HT but no significant differences were observed as seeds matured
528 from 14 to 20 DAP (Fig. 2e). The expression of BnaCYP707A1 (LOC111208232) and
529 BnaCYP707A4 (LOC106416608), which are involved in the ABA degradation pathway to form
530 PA and DPA, was significantly increased at 20SHT (Fig. 2e), which correlated with the reduced
531 ABA concentration in 20 DAP seeds from HT (Fig. 2a). Although the expression profiles of
532 genes involved in ABA metabolism support the reduced ABA levels in the seeds under HT, the
533 expression of ABA signalling genes BnaABI3 (LOC106361788 and LOC1064188223) and
534 BnaABI4 (LOC106443577), which promote seed dormancy, was increased in 14HT seeds,
535 while BnaABI5 (LOC106451127) was decreased (Fig. 2e). In older seeds, their expression was
536 not affected by HT. We further examined the expression pattern of some transcription factors
537 reported to regulate seed dormancy and seed germination. The expression of the AUXIN
538 RESPONSE FACTORS ARF10 and ARF16, which directly promote the expression of ABI3 (Liu *et*
539 *al.*, 2013) was not significantly changed in any of the comparisons (Fig. 5b). The AP2
540 transcription factor CHOTTO 1 (CHO1)/PLETHORA 5 (PLT5)/AINTEGUMENTA-like 5 (AIL5) acts
541 downstream of ABI4 during seed germination (Yamagishi *et al.*, 2009; Yano *et al.*, 2009).
542 Similar to ABI4, its expression was upregulated at 14HT and insignificant at 20 DAP (Fig. 5b).
543 DELAY OF GERMINATION 1 (DOG1) (Carrillo-Barral *et al.*, 2020), REDUCED DORMANCY 5
544 (RDO5)/DOG18 (Xiang *et al.*, 2014), RGA-like 2 (RGL2), and PHYTOCHROME INTERACTING
545 FACTOR 3-like 5 (PIL5) (Oh *et al.*, 2007), which are reported to promote dormancy, and
546 SPATULA (SPT) (Vaistij *et al.*, 2013), which plays an antagonistic role in dormancy regulation,
547 were up-regulated in 14HT, 18HT and 20HT seeds (Fig. 5b; Fig. S6; Table S4). HONSU, a seed-
548 specific protein phosphatase 2C that negatively regulates seed dormancy (Kim *et al.*, 2013),
549 was up-regulated in 14HT seeds, but down-regulated in later stages (Fig. 5b). The regulators
550 and markers of seed germination were up-regulated in HT seeds, supported by the overall
551 reduction in ABA levels in the whole seeds entering the maturation stage. However, the

552 regulators of seed dormancy were also up-regulated at all stages. These data suggest that the
 553 transcriptional behaviour of seed dormancy and germination regulators in HT-developing
 554 seeds is contradictory, making it difficult to draw conclusions.

555
 556 **Fig. 5** Transcriptional changes in Topas seeds associated with growth at HT indicate changes
 557 in cell wall composition. (a) Principal component analysis using gene expression data from the
 558 samples tested for differences between samples and biological replicates. (b) Heatmap
 559 showing differential transcription of selected genes involved in seed dormancy in 14 DAP, 18
 560 DAP, 20 DAP intact and 20 DAP SCR seeds. Expression in 14 DAP HT seeds is compared with
 561 expression in 18 DAP CT seeds. (c) GO terms related to cell wall associated with the
 562 transcriptional response of Topas seeds to HT are shown. (d) Heatmap showing the
 563 differential transcription of selected genes involved in pectin metabolism in 14 and 18 DAP
 564 seeds grown at CT and HT. The expression in 14 DAP HT seeds is compared with the expression
 565 in 18 DAP CT seeds. The full dataset is presented in Tables S1, S2 and S3.

566
 567 **The composition and properties of the seed coat cell wall are altered in HT-grown seeds**
 568 Gene ontology analysis revealed significant misregulation in many pathways
 569 related to plant cell walls (Fig. 5c). Interestingly, these included secondary cell wall biogenesis,
 570 cell wall thickening and modification, cellulose, pectin, and xyloglucan metabolism and
 571 modification pathways. Looking at the DEGs associated with pectin metabolic pathways, we

572 identified in 14HT and 18HT seeds the misregulation of enzymes such as
573 galacturonosyltransferases (GAUT) involved in pectin biosynthesis (Mohnen, 2008),
574 pectinmethylesterases and pectinmethylesterase inhibitors, involved in the chemical
575 modifications of pectin (Wormit & Usadel, 2018; Wu *et al.*, 2018; Xu *et al.*, 2022), and
576 polygalacturonases and pectate lyases, involved in pectin degradation (Marin-Rodriguez,
577 2002; Park *et al.*, 2010; Safran *et al.*, 2023) (Fig. 5d). This suggests that heat stress may
578 regulate the chemical modification of pectin, a major constituent of the cell wall.

579 To confirm whether the transcriptional changes in the cell wall-modifying enzymes affect the
580 pectin and lignin levels in the seed coat of HT-grown seeds, we used Ruthenium Red, which
581 stains the polyanionic molecules in the deesterified monomers of pectin in red (Nagayama *et*
582 *al.*, 2019), and Safranin-O, which has a high affinity for the phenolic compounds in lignin and
583 stains the walls bright red (Bond *et al.*, 2008) (Fig. 6a,b). The cells of the palisade layer in the
584 seed coat of 14 and 18 DAP Topas seeds grown under HT were strongly stained red with
585 Ruthenium Red and Safranin-O compared to the 14, 18 and 22 DAP seeds grown under CT.
586 The staining intensity increased with seed age. These observations suggest that seeds
587 entering the maturation phase accumulate more secondary cell wall elements in the seed
588 coat in HT than in CT.

589 Seed coat cell wall composition determines its mechanical strength (Mendu *et al.*, 2011;
590 Sechet *et al.*, 2018). The presence of pectin and hemicellulose in the seed coat layers was
591 investigated by immunostaining the seed coat with selective antibodies (Fig. 6d-g). For pectin,
592 which is mainly made of homogalacturonan (HG), we used the antibody LM19 that binds
593 preferentially to demethylesterified HG, the antibody LM20 that binds preferentially to
594 methylesterified HG, and the antibody JIM5, which has a high affinity for partially
595 demethylesterified HG (Fig. 6d-f). For hemicellulose, composed mainly of xyloglucan, the
596 LM25 antibody was used and combined with a pectolyase treatment to digest the pectin that
597 masks the hemicellulose (Fig. 6g). Fluorescence was quantified in the epidermal and palisade
598 layers of the seed coat. The seed coats of HT-developed 14 and 18 DAP seeds had significantly
599 higher levels of fluorescence of the LM19 and JIM5 antibody signals in the palisade layer,
600 indicating an increase in demethylesterified HG. In contrast, no significant differences in the
601 fluorescence intensity of the LM20 antibody signal were found in the cells of the palisade
602 layer in the testa of CT and HT seeds. In the epidermal layer of seeds developed under HT, the
603 signal for the JIM5 and LM19 antibodies was significantly higher in 14 DAP seeds, whereas the

604 signal for the LM20 antibody was significantly reduced at 18 DAP, indicating a reduction in
605 the amount of methylesterified HG. The results indicate an early enrichment of pectin and an
606 early shift towards demethylesterified pectin in the cell walls of the palisade and epidermal
607 cells in 14 DAP seeds grown under HT, with a significant reduction in the amount of
608 methylesterified HG molecules. LM25 fluorescence was significantly higher only in the
609 palisade cells of 18 DAP HT-grown seeds compared to CT seeds, suggesting a slight effect of
610 temperature on the amount of xyloglucan in the seed coat of these seeds (Fig. 6g).

611 To confirm our microscopic observations, we performed enzymatic fingerprinting of the cell
612 wall of the isolated seed coats from 10, 14 and 18 DAP seeds of Topas grown at CT and HT.
613 Digestion of HG by an endo-polygalacturonase between unmethylesterified ester stretches of
614 the galacturonic acid (GalA) releases several oligogalacturonans (OGs). OGs have been termed
615 GalAxMeyAcz based on the degree of polymerisation of GalA and the number of methyl and
616 acetyl groups. In our analysis of the Topas seed coat, we identified GalA3, GalA3ox, GalA3Xyl,
617 GalA3Me, GalA3MeAc, GalA4Ac, GalA4Me, GalA4Meox, GalA4Me-H₂O, and DP_x>4Mey
618 (methylesterified OGs with degree of polymerisation greater than 4). The total peak area
619 obtained from the MS analysis was plotted by grouping OGs with and without methyl groups
620 (Fig. 6h). A significant increase of unmethylesterified OGs was released from the cell walls of
621 14 DAP seed coat at HT compared to CT, which correlates with the signal intensity of the LM19
622 antibody binding to the unmethylesterified HGs in the cell walls in the seed coat layers (Fig.
623 6i,j). Similarly, a significant increase in the methylesterified OGs in the seed coats of 14 DAP
624 with varying numbers of methyl groups correlates with the signal intensity of JIM5 antibody
625 binding to partially methylesterified HGs in the cell walls of the epidermal and palisade layers
626 (Fig. 6i,j). It is worth noting the release of oxidized OGs, which might reflect the presence of
627 long oxidized OGs trapped with the pectin and not solubilized through alcohol extraction.
628 Regarding xyloglucan, LXXGAc levels did not change significantly and correlated with LM25
629 signal in the seed coat (Fig. 6k,l). However, a significant increase in the level of fucosylated
630 subunits is observed in the 14 DAP seed coats of HT compared to CT (Fig. 6k).

631 Using a variety of approaches, we found that growth on HT modified the cell wall properties
632 in the seed coat of seeds from 14 DAP onwards. The cell walls of the epidermal and palisade
633 cells accumulate more pectin and shift prematurely towards the production of
634 demethylesterified pectin, possibly making the cell wall stiffer.

635

637 **Fig. 6** The composition and properties of the seed coat cell wall are altered in HT-grown seeds.
638 (a, b) Histological sections of Topas seeds focused on the seed coat, stained with Ruthenium
639 Red for pectin (a) and Safranin-O for lignin (b). Sections of 14, 18, and 22 DAP CT seeds and
640 14 and 18 DAP HT seeds are shown. Scale bars represent 200 μm . (d-g) Immunolocalization
641 of pectin and xyloglucans using LM19, JIM5, LM20 and LM25 antibodies on the testa of 14
642 and 18 DAP HT and CT seeds. The signal is visible in green, the cell structure is marked in
643 magenta with calcofluor white. Scale bars represent 100 μm . Fluorescence intensity was
644 measured in epidermal and palisade cells in 10, 14 and 18 DAP HT and CT seeds. Asterisks
645 indicate statistically significant differences in HT and between seed ages in a one-way ANOVA
646 test with Tukey multiple comparisons (*, **, *** and **** correspond to p -values of $0.05 > p$
647 > 0.01 , $0.01 > p > 0.001$, $0.001 > p > 0.0001$ and $p < 0.0001$, respectively); n.s., not significant.
648 (h) Pectin composition of the seed coat cell wall of 10, 14, and 18 DAP seeds from HT and CT.
649 The graph shows the measurements expressed as peak area from the MS analysis for GalA3,
650 GalA3ox, GalA3Xyl, GalA3Me, GalA3MeAc, GalA4Ac, GalA4Me, GalA4Meox, GalA4Me-H₂O
651 and DP_x>4Mey (methylesterified OGs with degree of polymerisation greater than 4). (i) Graph
652 showing the total intensity signal for pectin from (d-f). (j) Graph showing the amount grouped
653 as methylesterified versus non-methylesterified OGs from (h). (k) Graph showing the
654 measurements presented as peak area from the MS analysis for xyloglucans. (l) Graph
655 showing the total intensity signal for xyloglucan from (g). Samples with the same letter were
656 not statistically significantly different. (m) A 3-mm silicon tube was applied to siliques from 10
657 DAP CT and 12 DAP HT. Dry seeds were quantified for the number of total viable, SCR and
658 dead seeds per silique. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences in HT and
659 between seed ages in a two-way ANOVA test with Tukey multiple comparisons (*, **, *** and
660 **** correspond to p -values of $0.05 > p > 0.01$, $0.01 > p > 0.001$, and $p < 0.001$, respectively);
661 n.s., not significant.

662

663 **Application of mechanical constraints during silique development partially rescues SCR** 664 **phenotype**

665 Since the seed coat thickness of seeds developed under HT was significantly reduced, we
666 suspected that such a seed coat would lack the strength to accommodate the developing
667 embryo. The continuous embryo growth would exert additional mechanical pressure on the
668 seed coat, resulting in SCR. To verify this, we applied a silicone tube to developing siliques to

669 provide an external mechanical constraint on the seeds in an attempt to compensate for the
670 early embryonic pressure on the seed coat (Fig. 6m). Such an experiment was previously
671 performed to show that an applied mechanical force on the siliques triggers seed maturation
672 by arresting embryonic growth (Rolletschek *et al.*, 2024). The presence of the silicone tube on
673 the siliques of CT plants did not affect the seed viability or promote SCR. In HT, the external
674 force exerted by the silicone tube on the silique (and thus on the seeds inside) resulted in a
675 significant decrease in the number of seeds undergoing SCR and an increase in the number of
676 viable seeds (Fig. 6m). The application of an external mechanical support reinforced the
677 compromised mechanical strength of the seed coat caused by the faster embryo
678 development.

679

680 **DISCUSSION**

681 Rising global temperatures adversely affect the production of major staple crops (Agnolucci
682 *et al.*, 2020; Jägermeyr *et al.*, 2021), by hindering proper seed development, as in *Brassica*
683 *napus* (Máková *et al.*, 2022). The occurrence of temperature-induced preharvest seed
684 sprouting was reported in our previous study in three spring cultivars of *B. napus* (Máková *et*
685 *al.*, 2022). In particular, prolonged cultivation of Topas at temperatures above the suboptimal
686 temperature resulted in half of the seeds per silique undergoing SCR. In this study, we have
687 elucidated the molecular mechanism behind the regulation of the SCR phenotype that occurs
688 in Topas during seed maturation.

689 Genetic screens in *Arabidopsis* have identified the molecular components involved in seed
690 maturation and dormancy (Finkelstein *et al.*, 2002; Holdsworth *et al.*, 2008). Reduced ABA
691 levels or increased levels of active GAs result in reduced seed dormancy (Benech-Arnold &
692 Rodríguez, 2018; Tai *et al.*, 2021). Although HT conditions during seed maturation (after 20
693 DAP) in Topas resulted in reduced ABA levels, suggesting reduced seed dormancy, there were
694 no differences between SCR and non-SCR seeds. Furthermore, the failure of *in vitro* ABA
695 treatment to rescue SCR led to the hypothesis of a minimal role for ABA in SCR. No direct
696 conclusions could be drawn linking the state of dormancy to the SCR phenotype, as even the
697 genes reported to positively regulate seed dormancy, such as *ABI3*, *ABI4*, *DOG1*, *RDO5*, *CHO1*,
698 and *SPT*, have increased expression levels in seeds developed on HT, but still lead to SCR.

699 Growth at elevated temperatures accelerated embryo development in *B. napus* from early
700 developmental stages (Máková *et al.*, 2022). Indeed, most of the embryos from 6 DAP seeds

701 produced at optimal growth temperature were at the 8-cell stage, whereas at elevated
702 temperatures, they were at the mid to late globular stage. A similar difference was observed
703 in the maturation phase, with a difference of 4 days for equivalent developmental stages. As
704 a result, embryos were larger in seeds that did not enlarge, possibly exerting mechanical
705 pressure on the seed coat. Mechanical constraints applied to developing seeds of *B. napus* cv.
706 Reston promoted seed maturation by activating the storage metabolism and the expression
707 of genes involved in the embryo maturation process (Rolletschek *et al.*, 2024). The higher
708 levels of ABA in 14 and 18 DAP embryos developed under HT and the increased expression
709 pattern of *ABI3* and *DOG1* in HT seeds during early maturation suggest that seed development
710 under elevated growth temperature could promote an early maturation process (Baud *et al.*,
711 2016; Leprince *et al.*, 2016; Rolletschek *et al.*, 2024).

712 The proper exchange of signals between the seed coat, endosperm, and embryo interacts to
713 define the final size, shape, and dormancy state of the seed at the end of the maturation
714 phase (Li *et al.*, 2019). The *Arabidopsis iku2-2 zou-4* double mutant has reduced seed viability
715 due to developing seeds undergoing testa rupture (Creff *et al.*, 2015), similar to the SCR
716 phenotype observed in Topas. The mutation in *HAIKU2 (IKU2)* results in increased endosperm
717 pressure, favouring mechanosensitive precocious testa stiffening, possibly dependent on
718 demethylesterified pectin accumulation. This results in small *iku2* seeds (Creff *et al.*, 2023).
719 Seeds of *zhoupi-4 (zou-4)* have a persistent endosperm at the torpedo stage, even as the
720 embryo expands in size, producing large seeds during development (Creff *et al.*, 2015). Testa
721 rupture in *iku-2 zou-4* seeds would be a consequence of early testa stiffening together with
722 increased pressure from the developing embryo and a persistent endosperm. Both *IKU2* and
723 *ZOU* expression were down-regulated in Topas seeds developed at high temperatures (Fig. S6
724 and Table S2), suggesting that a similar process may occur in *B. napus*.

725 GO enrichment analysis of the seed transcriptome revealed a temperature-dependent
726 misregulation of cell wall-related pathways in seeds. Pathways related to cellulose, pectin and
727 xyloglucan metabolism, cell wall thickening, and pectin modification were overrepresented.
728 The primary cell wall is composed of cellulose, hemicellulose, and pectin (Cosgrove, 2024),
729 while the secondary cell wall can be stiffened with lignin. Cellulose and hemicellulose are
730 embedded in a gel matrix formed by pectin and influence the extensibility of the cell wall, an
731 essential feature for cell growth and morphogenesis (Peaucelle *et al.*, 2011). Many genes
732 involved in pectin biosynthesis, modification, and degradation were misregulated, which led

733 us to investigate the methylesterification pattern of pectin, which could influence wall
734 rheology. Ruthenium Red staining for pectin and Safranin-O staining for lignin indicated that
735 both pectin and lignin levels were increased in the palisade layer of HT seed coats.
736 Immunostaining with pectin-specific antibodies and cell wall profiling of the seed coat of early
737 maturing seeds indicated that the overall pectin composition was altered, particularly in the
738 palisade layer. The significant enrichment of demethylesterified pectin in the palisade layer
739 of early maturing seeds developed under HT suggests that the seed coat cell walls may be
740 stiffer when grown at elevated temperatures.

741 The embryo stage and size difference observed in HT seeds may exert increased pressure on
742 the walls of the developing seed coat for the same overall seed size, resulting in increased
743 tension between adjacent cells within an integument layer. The reduction in the thickness of
744 the epidermal, palisade and endothelial cell layers of the seed coat observed in HT seeds
745 suggests that increased tension was exerted between adjacent cells and that the seed coat
746 cells resisted the tension by cell stretching rather than cell division. Such stress-dependent
747 stiffening of seed coat cell walls has been shown in *iku2* mutants (Creff *et al.*, 2023). Thus,
748 increased stiffness of the seed coat cell walls would resist strain between seed coat cells to
749 compensate for the pressure exerted by the developing embryo. Tight regulation of these
750 opposing forces governs the wall mechanics required for seed growth. Mechanical support of
751 Topas seeds developed under HT by applying a silicone tube partially rescued SCR, strongly
752 suggesting that the seed coat layers lack the strength to withstand the tension from the
753 pressure exerted by the developing embryo. The exact process by which increased pectin
754 demethylesterification plays a role in the wall mechanics of *Brassica napus* seeds is unclear.
755 Our data suggest two possible mechanisms underlying the heat-induced SCR phenotype. First,
756 exposure of seeds to elevated temperatures leads to changes in the seed coat cell wall,
757 making it more susceptible to rupture under the pressure exerted by the expanding embryo.
758 Second, HT-dependent embryo expansion increases the tension on the seed coat and may
759 promote the observed changes in cell wall composition, similar to what happens in
760 *Arabidopsis*. However, these changes may not be sufficient to prevent SCR due to the intense
761 pressure exerted by the growing embryo.

762

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773

774 **COMPETING INTERESTS**

775 The authors declare no competing interests.

776

777 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

778 HSR secured the funding. UK and HSR conceived the project, designed the experiments, and
779 interpreted the data. UK performed the seed phenotyping, histology, ABA treatments,
780 transcriptomics, and immunolabelling of the seed coat. IU and JH optimised the protocol for
781 Technovit embedding of oilseed rape seed and prepared the slides for histology. AMM
782 analysed the transcriptomic data. AC and BL performed the immunolabelling of the seed coat.
783 AV performed the cell wall profiling. IP, AP and ON performed the hormonal profiling. UK and
784 HSR drafted the manuscript. All authors have proofed and approved the manuscript.

785

786 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

787 The data generated during the current study are included in this published article (and its
788 Supporting Information file) and are available in the Zenodo repository
789 [<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.14224074>]. The dataset supporting the conclusions
790 of this article is deposited to the NCBI repository (BioProject accession number
791 PRJNA1188476, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA1188476>).

792

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- 944
- 945

946 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

947 **Fig. 1.** SCR phenotype observed in Topas seeds developed under HT. (a, b) 26 DAP seeds (a)
948 and their isolated embryos (b) grown under CT. (c, d) 26 DAP seeds (c) and their isolated
949 embryos (d) grown under HT. SCR was observed (*, Δ , +, \bullet). * Indicates seeds with testa
950 rupture with intact embryo, Δ indicates testa rupture with radicle protrusion, + indicates testa
951 rupture with cotyledon protrusion, and \bullet indicates embryos with abnormal development. (e)
952 Quantification of the number of dry seeds per silique from CT (blue) and HT (red) showing the
953 number of total, viable, SCR and dead seeds. Asterisks indicate statistically significant
954 differences in HT in a multiple t-test using the Holm-Sidak method (**** corresponds to p -
955 values of $p < 0.0001$). (f) Embryo stage of seeds developed on CT (top) and HT (bottom) from
956 14 to 20 DAP. The isolated embryo shown on the right is from the seed on the left. Scale bars:
957 2 mm (a-d) and 3mm (f).

958

959 **Fig. 2.** ABA levels and expression of genes involved in ABA metabolism in *Brassica napus* Topas
960 seeds. (a) Seeds were from 14 DAP to 36 DAP of CT (blue) and HT (red, dark red). From 20
961 DAP, HT seeds were separated into intact seeds (red) and SCR seeds (dark red). Quantification
962 is presented as pmol per g fresh weight. (b) Measurements were performed for ABA, 7-
963 hydroxy-ABA, phaseic acid (PA), and dihydrophaseic acid (DPA) from embryos and seed coats
964 from 14 DAP and 18 DAP seeds grown in CT (blue) and HT (red). Asterisks indicate statistically
965 significant differences in HT and between 14 DAP HT and 18 DAP CT in a multiple t-test using
966 the Holm-Sidak method (*, **, *** and **** correspond to p -values of $0.05 > p > 0.01$, 0.01
967 $> p > 0.001$, $0.001 > p > 0.0001$ and $p < 0.0001$, respectively); n.s., not significant. (c) 15 siliques
968 of 14 DAP and 18 DAP from HT and CT, respectively, were cultured in the presence or absence
969 of 10 μ M ABA (Fig. S1). Dry seeds were quantified for the number of total viable, SCR and
970 dead seeds per silique. Samples with the same letter were not statistically significantly
971 different. (d) Relative expression of selected genes representing DORMANCY ASSOCIATED
972 gene 1 (DRM1) and FRUCTOSE 1,6-BIPHOSPHATE ALDOLASE 6 (FBA6) in 14 DAP (blue), 20 DAP
973 intact (yellow) and 20 DAP SCR (grey) seeds. Data were extracted from the transcriptome
974 dataset (Tables S1 and S2). (e) Heatmap showing the differential expression of selected genes
975 involved in ABA metabolism in 14 DAP, 20 DAP intact, and 20 DAP SCR seeds. The full dataset
976 is provided in Tables S1 and S2.

977

978 **Fig 3.** Embryo and seed size measurements of *Brassica napus* Westar and Topas seeds
979 developed at CT and HT. (a, b) Seed (a) and embryo (b) area measurements in mm² of 14, 18
980 and 20 DAP Topas seeds developed at CT (blue) and HT (red). (c, d) Seed (c) and embryo (d)
981 area measurements in mm² of 14, 18 and 20 DAP Westar seeds developed at CT (blue) and
982 HT (red). Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences in HT and between 14 DAP HT
983 and 18 DAP CT in a two-way ANOVA test with Sidak's multiple comparisons (*, **, *** and
984 **** correspond to p -values of $0.05 > p > 0.005$, $0.005 > p > 0.0005$, $0.0005 > p > 0.0005$ and
985 $p < 0.00005$, respectively); n.s., not significant. (e) Embryo-to-seed size ratio in 14, 18 and 20
986 DAP Topas and Westar seeds developed at CT and HT. Samples with the same letter were not
987 statistically significantly different. Representative pictures of the seeds and embryos are
988 shown in Fig. S3.

989
990 **Fig. 4** The thickness of the seed coat cells is reduced in HT. (a-e) Histological sections of Topas
991 seeds focused on the seed coat, stained with toluidine blue. (a) The seed coat is composed of
992 an epidermal layer, a palisade layer and an endodermal layer. (b-e) Seed coat of 14 DAP seeds
993 from CT (b) and HT (d) and 18 DAP seeds from CT (c) and HT (e). Scale bars represent 200 μ m.
994 (f-h) Box-whisker plots show the size mean, median, outliers, and SD in μ m of the thickness
995 of the epidermal layer (f), palisade layer (g) and first endothelial cell layer (h) in 10, 14, 18,
996 and 20 DAP seeds from CT (blue) and HT (red). Samples with the same letter were not
997 statistically significantly different. (i) Percentage of reduction in thickness as the seed aged
998 from 14 to 20 DAP.

999
1000 **Fig. 5** Transcriptional changes in Topas seeds associated with growth at HT indicate changes
1001 in cell wall composition. (a) Principal component analysis using gene expression data from the
1002 samples tested for differences between samples and biological replicates. (b) Heatmap
1003 showing differential transcription of selected genes involved in seed dormancy in 14 DAP, 18
1004 DAP, 20 DAP intact and 20 DAP SCR seeds. Expression in 14 DAP HT seeds is compared with
1005 expression in 18 DAP CT seeds. (c) GO terms related to cell wall associated with the
1006 transcriptional response of Topas seeds to HT are shown. (d) Heatmap showing the
1007 differential transcription of selected genes involved in pectin metabolism in 14 and 18 DAP
1008 seeds grown at CT and HT. The expression in 14 DAP HT seeds is compared with the expression
1009 in 18 DAP CT seeds. The full dataset is presented in Tables S1, S2 and S3.

1010

1011 **Fig. 6** The composition and properties of the seed coat cell wall are altered in HT-grown seeds.

1012 (a, b) Histological sections of Topas seeds focused on the seed coat, stained with Ruthenium

1013 Red for pectin (a) and Safranin-O for lignin (b). Sections of 14, 18, and 22 DAP CT seeds and

1014 14 and 18 DAP HT seeds are shown. Scale bars represent 200 μm . (d-g) Immunolocalization

1015 of pectin and xyloglucans using LM19, JIM5, LM20 and LM25 antibodies on the testa of 14

1016 and 18 DAP HT and CT seeds. The signal is visible in green, the cell structure is marked in

1017 magenta with calcofluor white. Scale bars represent 100 μm . Fluorescence intensity was

1018 measured in epidermal and palisade cells in 10, 14 and 18 DAP HT and CT seeds. Asterisks

1019 indicate statistically significant differences in HT and between seed ages in a one-way ANOVA

1020 test with Tukey multiple comparisons (*, **, *** and **** correspond to p -values of $0.05 > p$

1021 > 0.01 , $0.01 > p > 0.001$, $0.001 > p > 0.0001$ and $p < 0.0001$, respectively); n.s., not significant.

1022 (h) Pectin composition of the seed coat cell wall of 10, 14, and 18 DAP seeds from HT and CT.

1023 The graph shows the measurements expressed as peak area from the MS analysis for GalA3,

1024 GalA3ox, GalA3Xyl, GalA3Me, GalA3MeAc, GalA4Ac, GalA4Me, GalA4Meox, GalA4Me-H₂O

1025 and DP_x>4Mey (methylesterified OGs with degree of polymerisation greater than 4). (i) Graph

1026 showing the total intensity signal for pectin from (d-f). (j) Graph showing the amount grouped

1027 as methylesterified versus non-methylesterified OGs from (h). (k) Graph showing the

1028 measurements presented as peak area from the MS analysis for xyloglucans. (l) Graph

1029 showing the total intensity signal for xyloglucan from (g). Samples with the same letter were

1030 not statistically significantly different. (m) A 3-mm silicon tube was applied to siliques from 10

1031 DAP CT and 12 DAP HT. Dry seeds were quantified for the number of total viable, SCR and

1032 dead seeds per silique. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences in HT and

1033 between seed ages in a two-way ANOVA test with Tukey multiple comparisons (*, **, *** and

1034 **** correspond to p -values of $0.05 > p > 0.01$, $0.01 > p > 0.001$, and $p < 0.001$, respectively);

1035 n.s., not significant.

1036

1037

1038 SUPPORTING INFORMATION

1039 Additional Supporting Information may be found online in the Supporting Information section

1040 at the end of the article.

1041 **Fig. S1** Representative picture of the silique culture system for ABA treatment.

1042 **Fig. S2** Profiles of auxin and its metabolites in *Brassica napus* Topas seeds, isolated embryos
1043 and seed coats.

1044 **Fig. S3** Representative pictures of the seeds and embryos measured in Fig. 3.

1045 **Fig. S4** Venn diagrams summarising the transcriptional response of Topas seeds to HT.

1046 **Fig. S5** GO terms associated with the transcriptional response of Topas seeds to HT.

1047 **Fig. S6** Expression clusters of the transcriptional response of Topas seeds to HT.

1048 **Table S1** Full dataset for the DEGs for all the comparisons.

1049 **Table S2** DEGs for dormancy, ABA and pectin metabolism related.

1050 **Table S3** Misregulated GO terms associated with plant cell wall, hormone, cell cycle,
1051 metabolic, heat response and developmental pathways.

1052 **Table S3** DEGs and GO terms associated with each of the clusters.

1053 **Methods S1** Co-expression cluster mapping of genes.